

AI-enabled Network Automation in TeraFlowSDN Orchestrated Networks

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Abstract—This paper explores the integration of AI in enhancing network orchestration within TeraFlowSDN. It highlights current contributions, such as the introduction of traffic forecaster and autonomous agent. Moreover, this paper presents a vision for future releases to enable secure, scalable, and adaptive network automation.

Index Terms—TeraFlowSDN, AI, agents, LLM, forecasting.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern telecommunication networks are rapidly evolving into highly dynamic, multi-layered ecosystems driven by the advent of 6G, edge computing, and cloud-native applications. As these networks expand in scale, diversity, and complexity, traditional network management and orchestration methods struggle to keep pace with the operational demands of service agility, real-time responsiveness, and cost-effectiveness [1]. To address these challenges, network automation promises to pave the path towards future networks. With this in mind, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) TeraFlowSDN project envisions a novel, cloud-native Network Automation Framework that combines automation, intelligence, and programmability to facilitate end-to-end service orchestration across heterogeneous network domains [2].

Within TeraFlowSDN’s open and modular framework, Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerges as a key enabler for advanced network automation. AI-driven techniques such as machine learning, predictive analytics, and knowledge-based reasoning can infer patterns in network data, predict anomalies before they degrade service quality, and optimize the utilization of resources under stringent latency constraints. By integrating AI-centric functionalities—ranging from forecasting traffic loads to orchestrating adaptive service policies, TeraFlowSDN provides novel levels of network resiliency and efficiency, ultimately enabling operators to deliver next-generation connectivity experiences.

This paper presents the design principles, enabling technologies, and real-world applications of AI-enabled network

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automation in TeraFlowSDN-orchestrated networks, offering insights into how this powerful synergy of Software Defined Networks (SDN) and AI evolves modern telecommunications.

II. INTENT AND LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

TeraFlowSDN introduces a variety of novel approaches to network automation, including the use of large language models (LLMs) to abstract and manage slice intent requests. Recent work in [3] introduces IntentLLM, an AI chatbot-based solution that leverages LLMs to create, find, and explain slice intents directly within the TeraFlowSDN controller. This approach allows network operators to express intents in human-friendly language, effectively bridging the gap between high-level service requirements and the underlying SDN-based orchestration processes. By doing so, TeraFlowSDN can interpret user requests more accurately, reduce manual configuration overhead, and accelerate the instantiation of new network slices or services.

The next step, is the introduction of Agentic framework to support network management. Figure 1 shows a multi-layer, AI-driven architecture in which an AgentTFS (agentic framework) uses Large Language Model (LLM) capabilities—classification, text interpretation, and retrieval-augmented generation—to process high-level user requests and translate them into network configurations. In the proposed security scenario, the AgentTFS generates Access Control Lists (ACLs) or policies that are then conveyed through the Southbound Interfaces (e.g., IETF ACL or T-API) to both IP and optical domains. Both IP and optical domains are synchronized by an End-to-End SDN Orchestrator (TFS), ensuring coordinated service delivery across IP and optical layers. Then, the IP SDN Controller (TFS) manages routers and other IP-based equipment, while the Optical SDN Orchestrator (TFS) controls optical switching elements in a transport network.

III. NETWORK DIGITAL TWINS

In tandem with AI-driven orchestration, Network Digital Twins (NDT) are becoming crucial to model, simulate, and predict network behaviors. According to [4], cloud-native SDN controllers such as TeraFlowSDN can integrate digital twin frameworks to enable proactive decision-making for optical and packet-optical networks.

By mirroring physical network elements and correlating real-time data with predictive analytics, operators can forecast

Fig. 1. AI-enabled AgentTFS to support Network Automation in TeraFlowSDN Orchestrated Networks.

network performance, detect vulnerabilities before they become service-impacting, and test new configurations in a risk-free virtual environment. This paradigm significantly enhances operational agility and reduces the time to market for novel services.

IV. TRAFFIC FORECASTING

Another key challenge in managing multi-layer networks lies in accurately forecasting traffic demands under varying load, mobility, and service conditions. References [5] and [6] present complementary AI-based approaches to traffic forecasting within TeraFlowSDN.

The work presented in [5] focuses on leveraging containerized microservices and ML pipelines to deliver highly scalable, real-time traffic predictions. By integrating the forecasting module with the TeraFlowSDN controller, operators can dynamically adapt routing and resource allocation in response to predicted traffic surges, thereby reducing congestion and improving overall Quality of Service (QoS).

The work presented in [6] introduces a hybrid AI model that blends statistical and machine learning techniques to forecast per-link demands. Incorporating such a model into TeraFlowSDN offers fine-grained visibility into traffic fluctuations at the link level, which is crucial for optimizing transport networks characterized by multi-hop topologies and mixed packet/optical segments.

V. ANOMALY DETECTION

Beyond traffic forecasting, maintaining robust network performance also hinges on swift detection and mitigation of anomalies. Work in [7] showcases how TeraFlowSDN can enhance anomaly detection capabilities by integrating SmartNIC Transceivers and advanced profiling techniques. These additions allow the controller to obtain deeper insights into traffic flow anomalies and potential hardware issues. By coupling the real-time telemetry data from SmartNICs with AI-driven anomaly detection models, TeraFlowSDN enables

proactive fault isolation and automated remediation workflows—minimizing service disruptions and guaranteeing more stable end-to-end performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

TeraFlowSDN stands at the forefront of the SDN evolution by combining cloud-native architectures, AI-based orchestration, and advanced functionalities like digital twins, traffic forecasting, and anomaly detection. The works referenced throughout this paper underscore the transformative potential of embedding intelligence into every layer of network management—from high-level intent-based configuration via LLMs to fine-grained insights gleaned through real-time telemetry and predictive models. As telecommunication networks continue to expand in scale and complexity, TeraFlowSDN’s automated, data-driven approach offers a clear path toward more resilient, adaptive, and user-centric connectivity services.

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